

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

M3.3 Development of a Web Repository with the Results of the Climate Change Evaluation

VERSION 1

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

This Milestone, namely M3.3, is part of Task 3.3 “Downscaling of future climate projections at the case-study scale and their transfer to the Partners” (Lead: UNIPR/ participants: UPV, UFZ, TUC, IST-ID, CERTE and BU), (Month 1 – Month 26). The aim of M3.3 is to outline the results of the climate change evaluation over the investigated pilot sites. For the future projections of the climate variables (precipitation and temperature), the data provided by EURO-CORDEX initiative under two emission scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) are used. The main information on the pilot sites, available data, analyses and results are presented. The data are freely downloadable from the web repository <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7247977>.

1. Introduction

InTheMED aims to develop innovative tools and methodologies for sustainable groundwater management in the MED in the context of climate change. The spatial and temporal heterogeneity of the climate in the MED underlines the need for local scale studies (D’Oria et al., 2018a, 2018b; Todaro et al., 2022). The objective of this work is to investigate the past and future local climate over the five pilot sites in the MED.

For each pilot site, precipitation and temperature records were analysed to evaluate the past climate and historical local trends. The future climate was assessed using the data provided by an ensemble of 17 climate models, which are combinations between General Circulation Models (GCMs) and Regional Climate Models (RCMs) developed under the framework of the EURO-CORDEX initiative (Jacob et al., 2014). Two Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) were considered: the RCP4.5 and the RCP8.5. The RCP4.5 is an intermediate scenario for which a radiative forcing in the year 2100 of 4.5 W/m² is projected; the peak of emissions is around 2040 and then they decline. The RCP8.5 is the most severe scenario with greenhouse gas emissions that continue rising throughout the century; the radiative forcing reached by 2100 is 8.5 W/ m². The RCM data are generally affected by systematic errors and need an adjustment. The bias correction was performed on the basis of the available observed data in a control historical period. The post-processed data were used to analyse the local future changes in precipitation and temperature at short- (2021-2040), medium- (2041-2060) and long-term (2076-2095).

For more details on the analysis presented in this report, see Todaro et al. (2022).

2. Pilot Sites and Available Data

The study areas are located in Portugal (Guadiana Basin), Spain (Requena-Utiel), Tunisia (Grombalia), Greece (Tympaki) and Turkey (Konya). The main characteristics of the pilot sites, depicted in Figure 1, are summarized in Table 1. In the following, the pilot sites will be identified with the abbreviations reported in Table 1.

Figure 1. Location of the five pilot sites.

For each pilot site, daily precipitation and mean temperature data were collected at gauging stations over the study areas in the period 1976-2005.

Among the available stations, only those that present time series with an amount of data higher than 70% were selected. For each station, the gaps in the records were filled according to a linear relationship with the best correlated neighbouring gauge (Allen et al., 1998). In the absence of contemporary daily information, the missing data were replaced with random values extracted from a normal (for temperature) and log-normal (for precipitation) distributions, with mean and standard deviation of the recorded data. To preserve seasonality, this method was applied on monthly scale (i.e. each month of the available sample has its own mean and standard deviation). In case of precipitation, the probability of no-rain was preserved.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the five pilot sites.

Nation	Pilot site name	Abbreviation	Size (km ²)	Rain gauge	Temperature gauge
Greece	Tympaki	PS-GRE	58	2	1
Spain	Requena-Utiel	PS-SPA	1285	8	1
Portugal	Guadiana Basin	PS-POR	11594	60	4
Tunisia	Grombalia	PS-TUN	391	6	1
Turkey	Konya	PS-TUR	50000	18	18

Regarding the future precipitation and temperature data, the climate projections of the EURO-CORDEX initiative were considered. To account for the uncertainty of the climate model projections, an ensemble of 17 GCM-RCM combinations with a grid resolution of about 12.5 km (EUR-11 grid) under the RCP4.5 and the RCP8.5 scenarios were analysed. Table 2 reports the GCM-RCM combinations used in this work. The models provide results on a regular grid; a downscaling procedure based on an interpolation method was then performed to obtain the climate variables at each gauging station locations. In particular, we used an inverse squared distance method by processing the values of the climate models in the nine cells closest to the location of the gauge; for details, see D’Oria et al. (2017). The climate model outputs present systematic deviations from the observed data; therefore, a bias correction must be applied to obtain more reliable projections, especially when used for hydrological impact studies (Teutschbein and Seibert, 2010). In the present work, the bias correction was performed following the distribution mapping method (D’Oria et al., 2017, 2018; Teutschbein and Seibert, 2012) which ensures that cumulative distribution functions of the climate model data, at monthly scale, agree with the ones of the observed data in the control period.

Table 2. GCM-RCM models from EURO-CORDEX project (<https://www.euro-cordex.net/>). The ditto mark “ indicates repetition of the above text.

	GCM		RCM	
	Institute	Model	Institute	Model
1	CNRM-CERFACS	CNRM-CM5	CLMcom	CCLM4-8-17
2	“	“	SMHI	RCA4
3	“	“	KNMI	RACMO22E
4	ICHEC	EC-EARTH	KNMI	RACMO22E
5	“	“	SMHI	RCA4
6	“	“	CLMcom	CCLM4-8-17
7	“	“	DMI	HIRHAM5
8	IPSL	IPSL-CM5A-MR	IPSL	WRF381P
9	“	“	SMHI	RCA4
10	“	“	IPSL-INERIS	WRF331F
11	MOHC	HadGEM2-ES	DMI	HIRHAM5
12	“	“	CLMcom	CCLM4-8-17
13	“	“	KNMI	RACMO22E
14	“	“	SMHI	RCA4
15	MPI-M	MPI-ESM-LR	CLMcom	CCLM4-8-17
16	“	“	SMHI	RCA4
17	NCC	NorESM1-M	DMI	HIRHAM5

3. Results

In this section, the historical and future local variations in the precipitation and temperature time series are presented. For the sake of brevity and to give an overview of the five different regions, the results weighted over the entire study areas are reported. For each pilot site, the areal values were computed from the gauging station data using the Thiessen polygon method.

The historical values were compared with the estimates evaluated over twenty-year periods so defined: reference period (1986-2005), short-term (2021-2040), medium-term (2041-2060) and long-term (2076-2090).

Historical Data

Table 3 reports the values of the annual mean temperature and total annual precipitation in the reference period 1986-2005 for each pilot site. The data highlight variations from one site to another. The warmest area is PS-TUN with an average annual mean temperature of 18.8 °C; the coldest site is PS-TUR with 11.4 °C. The temperature variability in the reference period (Min/Max) is the highest for PS-TUR (9.9/13.1 °C) and the smallest for PS-TUN (18.0/19.4 °C). Looking at the annual average precipitation, PS-TUR is also the driest pilot site (355 mm) and PS-POR is the wettest zone (545 mm). The minimum precipitation variability is observed for PS-TUR (264/458 mm) while the maximum for PS-TUN (291/1092 mm).

Table 3. Annual mean temperature and total annual precipitation for the five pilot sites. The table reports the average, minimum (Min) and maximum (Max) values in the reference period 1986-2005.

	Mean temperature (°C)			Precipitation (mm)		
	Average	Min	Max	Average	Min	Max
PS-GRE	16.2	15.4	17.4	474	268	763
PS-POR	16.1	15.1	17.4	545	322	1018
PS-SPA	13.8	12.2	15.0	434	281	642
PS-TUN	18.8	18.0	19.4	507	291	1092
PS-TUR	11.4	9.9	13.1	355	264	458

The historical trends of the annual mean temperature and annual precipitation were analysed in the period 1976-2005 making use of the Mann-Kendall test at the 5% significance level and quantifying them through the Theil-Sen estimator. Table 4 reports the results for each pilot

site and for the two variables. The temperature presents an upward trend for all study areas. The highest gradient is observed for TUR (+0.5 °C/decade); the other investigated MED regions are warming at a rate of +0.2÷0.3 °C/decade. The temperature trend is always significant, except for GRE. The precipitation trends do not indicate remarkable variations; a decreasing trend is observed for GRE, POR and TUR, with the maximum negative for POR of about -28 mm/decade; SPA and TUN exhibit an increasing trend with a maximum gradient of +23 mm/decade for TUN. For all pilot sites, the total annual precipitation trend is not statistically significant.

Table 4. Annual historical trends of temperature and precipitation and trend significance at the 5% level H (0, no significant; 1, significant) in the period 1976-2005.

	Temperature		Precipitation	
	Trend (°C/decade)	H	Trend (mm/decade)	H
GRE	+0.2	0	-26	0
POR	+0.3	1	-28	0
SPA	+0.3	1	+5	0
TUN	+0.3	1	+23	0
TUR	+0.5	1	-16	0

Future Climate Projections

The outputs of 17 RCM climate models, once downscaled and bias corrected, were considered to investigate the future climate over the MED under two different scenarios: RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. Figure 2 and Figure 3 show the annual mean temperature and the total annual precipitation for the period 1976-2098, for each pilot site and in terms of 10-year moving average, which allows to highlight the climate change signal against natural variability. According to Figure 2, an increase in temperature is expected for the future for all pilot sites and for both scenarios. The warming of the areas is particularly evident for the RCP8.5. Regarding the precipitation (Figure 3), according to both scenarios, the variability between the 17 climate models is high, pointing out a large uncertainty of the climate model projections. GRE and POR, according to the median values, show a decrease in precipitation for the future; on the contrary, SPA, TUN and TUR do not show significant changes.

Figure 2. Annual mean temperature in terms of 10-year moving average projected by the 17 RCMs for all pilot sites in the period 1976-2098. The two emission scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 are reported.

Figure 3. Annual precipitation in terms of 10-year moving average projected by the 17 RCMs for all pilot sites in the period 1976-2098. The two emission scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 are reported.

Table 5 and Table 6 summarize the mean temperature and precipitation in terms of RCM ensemble median on a seasonal and annual scale. They report the observed and simulated variables for the reference period and their variations with respect to the climate projections for the three future periods, under the two emission scenarios. The robustness of the change, which represents the level of agreement across the 17 RCMs, is indicated. The change is robust if more than 66% of the climate models (11 out of 17) agree in the direction of the change according to the RCM ensemble median.

Regarding the temperature (Table 5), the analysis on the three future periods indicates a progressive warming over all the areas investigated and for both RCP scenarios; the mean temperature increases in all seasons compared to the reference period. The changes are always robust. For GRE, SPA and TUN the maximum temperature increase is expected during the summer season with a long-term increase under the RCP8.5 of 4.73 °C, 4.99 °C and 4.32 °C, respectively. For POR, the maximum is found in the autumn season with an increase of 4.22 °C, at long-term under the RCP8.5. The highest temperature increase is expected for TUR; the maximum is in the spring season for the RCP8.5, at long term (5.43 °C).

Regarding the precipitation (Table 6), the analysis indicates positive and negative variations, on a seasonal and annual scale, with respect to the reference period. The changes are not always robust. For GRE, the maximum increment is detected in the autumn season (+9.9%) at short-term and for the RCP4.5, the highest decrease is expected in the winter season (-30.7%) at long-term and for the RCP8.5. The summer precipitation was set equal to zero as the observed and estimated precipitations are always less than 1 mm. For POR, the precipitation variation is mostly negative; the highest decrease is in the summer season (-61.3%) at long-term for the RCP8.5; the maximum increment is detected in the winter season (+13.6%) at long-term for the RCP4.5. For SPA, the highest precipitation decrease is expected during the summer season at long-term for the RCP8.5 (-38.1%) and the highest precipitation increment is expected during the autumn season at medium-term for the RCP8.5 (+8.6%). For TUN, the highest decrease is in the summer season at long-term for the RCP8.5 (-34.0%) and the maximum increment is expected in the autumn season at long-term for the RCP4.5 (+9.2%). For TUR, the highest decrease is found in the summer season at long-term for the RCP8.5 (-28.5%), while the maximum increment is expected in the autumn season at short-term for

the RCP4.5 (+10.4%). It is noteworthy that the inter-model variability of the precipitation data is high, as highlighted in Figure 3, leading to a large uncertainty about RCM precipitation projections.

Table 5. Seasonal and annual mean temperature (°C) over the five pilot sites: observed values (Obs.) and RCM median values for the reference period (1986-2005). Temperature change (°C) between the RCM medians at the short- (2021-2040), medium- (2041-2060) and long-term (2076-2095) and those evaluated in the reference period, for the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. The symbol * indicates a robust change. The colour scale (from white to red) highlights the change rate.

		Obs.	RCM	RCP4.5			RCP8.5		
		RP	RP	ST	MT	LT	ST	MT	LT
GRE	Spring	15.48	15.58	+0.97*	+1.63*	+2.26*	+1.24*	+2.32*	+4.69*
	Summer	25.20	25.13	+1.15*	+1.81*	+2.53*	+1.38*	+2.21*	+4.73*
	Autumn	19.10	19.11	+0.82*	+1.52*	+2.35*	+1.25*	+2.16*	+4.21*
	Winter	10.86	11.04	+0.97*	+1.33*	+1.95*	+0.98*	+1.76*	+3.77*
	Year	17.66	17.72	+1.00*	+1.48*	+2.20*	+1.22*	+2.08*	+4.29*
POR	Spring	14.86	14.56	+0.88*	+1.31*	+1.63*	+0.82*	+1.68*	+3.45*
	Summer	23.87	23.66	+0.84*	+1.70*	+1.87*	+1.09*	+1.83*	+4.09*
	Autumn	17.30	17.45	+1.09*	+1.75*	+2.20*	+1.35*	+2.21*	+4.22*
	Winter	9.65	9.83	+0.79*	+0.92*	+1.41*	+0.80*	+1.43*	+2.64*
	Year	16.42	16.37	+0.81*	+1.37*	+1.75*	+1.00*	+1.72*	+3.64*
SPA	Spring	12.09	11.83	+0.84*	+1.46*	+1.75*	+0.94*	+1.88*	+3.56*
	Summer	22.44	22.26	+1.32*	+1.94*	+2.55*	+1.34*	+2.43*	+4.99*
	Autumn	14.09	14.27	+1.25*	+1.80*	+2.42*	+1.34*	+2.26*	+4.40*
	Winter	6.43	6.67	+0.97*	+1.10*	+1.7*	+0.95*	+1.62*	+3.33*
	Year	13.76	13.76	+0.97*	+1.47*	+1.97*	+1.10*	+1.98*	+4.04*
TUN	Spring	16.56	16.40	+0.78*	+1.09*	+1.69*	+0.88*	+1.62*	+3.23*
	Summer	25.76	25.52	+1.29*	+1.67*	+2.27*	+1.34*	+2.2*	+4.32*
	Autumn	20.41	20.34	+0.98*	+1.40*	+2.04*	+1.01*	+1.92*	+3.80*
	Winter	12.38	12.61	+0.76*	+0.97*	+1.44*	+0.64*	+1.45*	+3.01*
	Year	18.78	18.72	+0.90*	+1.30*	+1.89*	+0.98*	+1.85*	+3.61*
TUR	Spring	10.26	10.41	+1.11*	+1.74*	+2.68*	+1.27*	+2.64*	+5.43*
	Summer	21.66	21.45	+1.23*	+2.02*	+2.53*	+1.49*	+2.53*	+4.92*
	Autumn	12.12	12.24	+0.94*	+1.75*	+2.35*	+1.52*	+2.39*	+4.62*
	Winter	0.56	0.95	+1.51*	+2.15*	+3.27*	+1.58*	+2.61*	+5.35*
	Year	11.15	11.26	+1.18*	+1.86*	+2.73*	+1.62*	+2.78*	+5.19*

Table 6. Seasonal and annual precipitation (mm) over the five pilot sites: observed value (Obs.) and RCM median values for the reference period (1986-2005). Precipitation change (%) between the RCM medians at the short- (2021-2040), medium- (2041-2060) and long-term (2076-2095) and those evaluated in the reference period, for the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. The symbol * indicates a robust change. The colour scale highlights positive (blue) and negative (gold) change rates.

	Obs.	RCM	RCP4.5			RCP8.5			
			RP	RP	ST	MT	LT	ST	MT
GRE	Spring	76	81	+4.7	-4.4	-12.7	+2.0	-9.2	-29.8
	Summer	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Autumn	130	126	+9.9*	+1.5*	-14.0	+4.8*	-8.8	-23.5
	Winter	267	300	-7.8*	-7.1*	-11.2*	+1.8	-7.8*	-30.7*
	Year	474	513	-4.1	-9.3	-15.7	-1.8	-13.5	-23.5
POR	Spring	136	135	-4.0*	-17.1*	-19.1*	+4.7	-22.9*	-33.2*
	Summer	20	23	-15.6*	-42.8*	-29.3*	-29.7*	-27.4*	-61.3*
	Autumn	182	183	-17.3*	-19.0*	-21.3*	-19.0*	-23.4*	-34.6*
	Winter	206	210	+3.5	-0.7	+13.6	-2.7	-2.0	-6.2
	Year	545	546	-2.6	-12.9	-9.5	-8.8	-14.3	-22.9
SPA	Spring	116	116	-6.3*	-5.1*	-14.9*	-2.2*	-3.4*	-24.2*
	Summer	61	64	+7.5*	-6.1	-14.0	+0.7*	-7.3	-38.1
	Autumn	151	144	-10.1*	-9.1*	-6.0*	-2.5*	+8.6	-5.1*
	Winter	107	104	+0.8	+1.3	+3.3	+2.9	+1.7	-1.3
	Year	434	429	-3.1*	-2.6*	-3.9*	+1.4	+0.2	-18.5*
TUN	Spring	95	107	-19.4*	-20.9*	-21.3*	-11.7*	-19.7*	-28.8*
	Summer	32	25	+3.8	-15.0	-17.9	-5.3	-9.4	-34.0
	Autumn	175	187	-9.2	-2.6	+9.2	-2.0	-0.3	-10.1
	Winter	205	195	-3.0*	-0.3*	-2.4*	-4.0*	-7.2*	-10.5*
	Year	507	500	-0.2	-0.4	-0.9	+0.7	-5.8	-16.0
TUR	Spring	120	122	+1.6	+6.8	+5.4	+3.6	-2.8	-8.2
	Summer	39	39	-17.2*	-27.0*	-12.7*	-19.9*	-20.7*	-28.5*
	Autumn	80	78	+10.4*	+10.2*	+4.4*	+6.6*	+2.5*	-2.7
	Winter	116	126	+2.9	+9.6	+4.5	+3.7	+4.8	+6.0
	Year	355	366	+1.8	+3.1	+2.1	+2.1	-2.7	-2.0

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